

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CYNICISM AND SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS' BEHAVIOURS OF FAVOURITISM

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between teachers' perception of organizational cynicism and school administrators' behaviours of favouritism. Since the research is a study that was carried out in order to detect the relationship between favouritism and cynicism, it is in correlational survey model. The sample of the research is constituted by 242 teachers who work in formal elementary schools in Van province. "Favouritism Scale in School Management" and "Organizational Cynicism Scale" were used to collect data for the study. Average, standard deviation, t-test, variance analysis, and regression, which are from descriptive statistics, were used in the analysis of the data. As a result of the study, it was observed that teachers' levels related to their perception of behaviours of favouritism of school administrators and their perception of organizational cynicism are low. Female teachers perform more cynical behaviours compared to male teachers. It has been observed that teachers working in schools which have 40 or more teachers have less cynicism and favouritism perceptions compared to other groups. It has been observed that there is not a significant difference between favouritism and cynicism perceptions of teachers by class, branch, or period of service. It has been observed that there is a significant, positive, and medium level of relationship between favouritism and organizational cynicism. In the scope of this study, it has been

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observed that the perception of favouritism in schools is a significant predictor of organizational cynicism level.

Keywords: favouritism, cynicism, teachers, school administrators

1. Introduction

Unlike many organizations, educational institutions are dynamic structures where human relations are at the highest level. Leadership behaviours of education administrators and their level of behaving within codes of conduct positively or negatively affect the attitudes of the institution staff towards the institution.

While the managers who consider the concepts such as democracy, equality, accountability, transparency, rights, and justice in managerial activities are appreciated by the institution staff, managers who do not take these concepts into consideration are criticized (Erdem & Meriç, 2013). Favouritism is the primary unethical behaviour (Aydoğan, 2009; Polat & Kazak, 2014). According to Albright and Carr (1997), ongoing favouritism within the institution prevents accurate decision-making and it causes lack of motivation among staff. This situation affects the productivity of both organizations and staff in a negative way. For this reason, favouritism is likened to a cancer in the institution.

Favouritism has had the primary effect in political decision-making process for ages. Although the perception of democracy has become widespread in the twenty-first century, the perception of favouritism-based administration has still continued (Kuznar & Frederich, 2007). While several legal frames have been formed to prevent favouritism in countries where level of welfare is at the desired level, favouritism has still continued to be an accepted fact in developing countries (Boadi, 2000). The results of the study by Araslı & Tümer (2008) showed that nepotism was identified as the reasons of the job stress and increased dissatisfaction of employees. Nepotism was identified as the greatest factor affecting job stress.

The fact that in educational organizations, criteria of favouritism, influential contact, relative, and being in the closer environment have come to the forefront rather than qualification, skill, equality, and justice negatively affects the efficiency of these organizations. In the study in which Aydoğan (2009) attempted to detect the notion of favouritism in Turkish Educational System, it was stated that favouritism has been very common in educational system and especially administrators have favoured their friends, fellow townsmen, and people who have similar political views with them.

Educational institutions are living structures of which raw material and product are human. Educational institutions are also influenced by many different factors such as the attitudes, lifestyles, beliefs and individual characteristics of their staff just like other institutions or even more than them. Attitudes and approaches of administrators which provoke distrust have caused negative opinions and attitudes in staff towards the organization. Staff's negative opinions and attitudes towards the organization may cause

cynicism (Kalağan & Güzeller, 2010). Organizational cynicism is a term which is related to organizational culture that has important effects on school efficiency, teacher performance, and success of students. Cynicism in educational organizations arises especially as negative belief, emotions, and behaviours of teachers towards the school (Akın, 2015).

2. Literature Review

It is important to explain the concepts of cynicism and favouritism to detect the relationship between cynicism and favouritism practices which are one of the leading factors of cynicism and determine the attitudes of employees towards the organization:

2.1 Favouritism

As one of the important problems of public bureaucracy, favouritism (Yılmaz & Kılavuz, 2002) is the fact that the officer performing the public affairs unjustly or unlawfully favour one or more persons (Gönülaçar, 2012). Favouritism is discussed in two subgroups in the literature as being “personal favouritism” and “political favouritism”. Personal favouritism (Nepotism & Cronyism) is that in the employment or the promotion of the staff, it is not considered who deserves it but the ones who are relatives, friends, fellow townsmen, colleagues or from the same tribe are considered. On the other hand, political favouritism (patronage, clientelism, and services favouritism) is that after they come to the power, political parties get unfair advantage by taking privileged actions in various ways for power bases who support them. Types of favouritism are presented in Figure 1 (Asunakutlu & Avcı, 2010; Özkanan & Erdem, 2014).

Figure 1: Classification of favouritism types

Nepotism is the fact that when a person is employed as public officer or inducted or promoted, measures such as success, skill, level of education, ability etc. are not taken into consideration but only their relationship by affinity with bureaucrats, politicians, or public officers is taken into consideration. The ones who present such favouritism behaviours act emotionally due to the effects of such relationship (Özsemerci, 2003).

Although people react less against nepotism compared to other ways of corruption (Karakas & Çak, 2007), it is observed as the most common way of corruption which is not based on benefit. As a type of nepotism, tribalism is favouritism of people from the same tribe or clan just because they are from the same tribe or clan. Disregarding factors such as skill, ability, success, and level of education (qualification), it is to employ or promote one person in public institutions or in private business just because they are from the same tribe or clan (Asunakutlu & Avci, 2010; Özkanan & Erdem, 2014).

Cronyism means that in procedures such as employment, promotion, or rewarding, a person who is out of family but a close friend or fellow is preferred instead of considering objective criteria such as a person's skills, success, and educational level. Cronyism is the positive treatment, in other words, favouritism of some people due to their close relationships with people who work at key points. In this type of favouritism, the motto "*It does not matter what you know or which skills you have, who you meet or know is important*" is adopted (Büte, 2011; Karakas & Çak, 2007; Khatri & Tsang, 2003). Cronyism mostly occurs as the favouritism of closer environment in employment and tender bids (Karakas & Çak, 2007). Its difference from nepotism is that relationship by affinity is not in question in this type of favouritism. Widely seen in Turkey, "patriotism" (favouritism of fellow townsman) is a type of cronyism which is based on people's favouring of each other with people who are from the same region or city or the solidarity patterns between them (Özsemerci, 2003).

Political Favouritism (partisanship) means that after coming to power, political parties provide unfair benefits, privileged work or operations to groups which support the party. Political favouritism is also stated as "partisanship" or "political logrolling". Political favouritism is observed in three ways (Asunakutlu & Avci, 2010; Özkanan & Erdem, 2014);

- a) Patronage: It is the fact that after coming to the power, political parties dismiss "high-level bureaucrats" who work in public institutions and organizations and they assign new people to these positions by considering factors such as political logrolling, ideology, and nepotism-cronyism (Özsemerci, 2003: 28).
- b) Clientelism: It is the distribution of public resources to the circle of friends and political supporters through tender bids, privatization etc. instead of doing it to improve the quality of public properties and services (Keefer, 2007).
- c) Services Favouritism: It is the fact that a public officer provide service to his/her relatives in an unfair and illegal way (Benk & Karakurt, 2010).

When favouritism in school management is discussed within the scope of educational organizations, it can be defined as that school administrators illegally support and watch over people whom they feel close, and provide privileges and rights for them that s/he does not provide for others due to various reasons such as union membership, political opinion, patriotism, graduating from the same school, kinship, gender etc. (Erdem & Meriç, 2013). Act of favouritism is an important notion which negatively affects potential resources and power of school and teacher performances. Act of favouritism of school administrators stems from their concern of collecting power or

detect them and protecting themselves from other colleagues. The fact that school administrators have such concerns can be explained through the notions such as the power and the authority of rewarding and promotion which were provided by the status, the concern of being criticized, being a role model, and the relationship levels with other colleagues.

Attitudes and behaviours of favouritism of school administrators create negative effect especially on teachers and these effects cause alienation of teachers to their school and profession. The feeling of alienation that teachers experience damages their sense of belonging to the school and their trust in administrators. Moreover, acts of favouritism decrease motivation and satisfaction of teachers, create the feeling of exhaustion, make them feel they are under control, decrease their will to attend activities which were organized in school after classes, and make them avoid taking any responsibility apart from classes (Meriç, 2012; Pounder & Blase, 1988). This situation decreases the efficacy of school and causes the establishment of a negative organization culture.

In the research carried out by Polat and Kazak (2014), it was revealed that there was a significant and negative relationship between the attitudes and acts of favouritism of school administrators and teachers' perceptions of the organizational justice. It was also observed that favouritism is a significant predictor of organizational justice. It is seen that the number of studies on the relationship between favouritism in educational organizations and organizational cynicism is not sufficient (Karademir, 2016). The detection of the relationships between the attitudes of favouritism of school administrators and the cynical behaviour perceptions of teachers working in schools shall reveal important data in explaining and detecting negative attitudes and behaviours of teachers towards the school.

2.2 Organizational Cynicism

The term cynicism emerged in Ancient Greek times and it is based on "cynism" which is a philosophical movement emphasizing morality and rejecting earthly wishes and desires (Kasalak & Bilgin Aksu, 2014). In the dictionary of Turkish Language Association (TDK), cynicism is defined as cynism which is the doctrine of Antisthenes defending that humans can achieve morality and happiness by getting rid of all requirements without being connected to any values.

Organizational cynicism, on the other hand, is defined as "*people's act of nurturing negative attitudes and negative emotions such as distrust, hopelessness, anger and frustration towards the organization where people work*". Organizational cynicism is the whole of negative beliefs, emotions, and behaviours people have towards the organization. Employees might exhibit cynical behaviours such as not liking the environment they work, always complaining, always talking about pessimistic ideas, leaving the organization as soon as it becomes possible, having the feeling that they are cheated by their organization, being on a go slow, spending more time than necessary for a duty at the work by not using the time efficiently, asking for break, not being present at work despite having no excuse, dealing with things which are not related to the business, not

coming work on time, and dealing with other businesses by getting sick leave (Abraham, 2000; Dean et al., 1998; Erdost et al., 2007; Helvacı & Kılıçoğlu, 2018; James, 2005; Kalağan & Güzeller, 2010; Karademir, 2016).

The assumption that organizations lack principles of accuracy, honesty, justice, sincerity and candidness lies at the bottom of organizational cynicism (Torun & Üçok, 2014). Cynicism in educational institutions is negative attitudes of teachers towards the school organization. It is also defined as teachers' disbelief in the policies and practices at school and the idea that their administrators do not show their true characters (Helvacı & Çetin, 2012).

Organizational cynicism is generally discussed in three dimensions as being cognitive, affective, and behavioural (Ayık, Şayir & Bilici, 2016; Dean et al., 1998). In cognitive cynicism, employees have the belief that their institutions lack principles which form the organizational integrity such as justice, honesty, openness, and sincerity. For this reason, cynical employees think that the decisions their organizations and administrators make are based on benefit. Employees think that their organizations do not value their efforts, and hence they do not trust their organizations (Kutunis & Çetinel, 2010).

In affective cynicism, employees emotionally have negative feelings for their institutions. Employees nurture negative feelings towards their institutions such as rage, hatred, antipathy, fear, disgust, despisal, and even shame (Dean et al., 1998; Kalağan & Güzeller, 2010). In behavioural cynicism, employees turn their negative beliefs and emotions into behaviours. In this scope, employees do not behave sincere, honest, and open to their institutions; they pretend, exhibit ironic behaviours, and despise the institution or colleagues. Employees exhibit negative behaviours such as making pessimistic predictions about the future of the institution (Dean et al., 1998; Özgener, Ögüt & Kaplan, 2008).

In the study carried out by Bernerth, Armenakis, Feild and Walker (2007), it was revealed that there is a positive relationship between employees' perception of injustice and organizational cynicism behaviours. Similarly, in the studies carried out by Abraham (2000), Nafei (2013) and Yim and Moses (2016), it was stated that there is a negative relationship between teachers' perception of cynicism and their motivations. There are several studies which discuss the relationship between favouritism and various organizational variables. When the studies carried out in Turkey are analysed, it is observed that organizational variables such as favouritism (Aydın, 2016; Deniz, Gürer & Solmaztürk, 2016; Karademir, 2016), organizational silence (Demirtaş, Özdemir & Küçük, 2016), political discrimination (Keskinkılıç & Oğuz, 2016), organizational exclusion and alienation (Abaslı, 2018), organizational justice (Akar, 2018; Alkış & Kılınç, 2016; Dağlı & Akyol, 2019), organizational commitment (Akar, 2018; Yüksel & Şahin, 2017) have important effects on teachers' experience of organizational cynicism and are important predictors.

The main issue of this study is to determine the relationship between cynical behaviours of teachers and the favouritism behaviours of school administrators which

negatively affect the productivity of employees and the environment of school organization and to determine its predictive power. That the administrators of schools where teachers work exhibit behaviours of favouritism might cause teachers to exhibit negative attitudes and behaviours towards school. Therefore, favouritism and cynicism are factors which reduce the productivity of both school and teachers. For this reason, it is highly important to observe how much favouritism affects organizational cynicism.

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between teachers' perception of organizational cynicism and school administrators' behaviours of favouritism. For this purpose, following questions have been asked:

- 1) Is there a meaningful relationship between school principals' favoritist behaviors and the teachers' perception of organizational cynicism?
- 2) What is the level of the school principals' favoritist behaviors to predict teachers' perceptions of organizational cynicism?

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Model of Study

This study is in correlational survey model as it is a study carried out to determine the relationship between favouritism and cynicism. Correlational survey model is a research model which aims to detect the existence or degree of covariance between two and more variables (Balci, 2010; Karasar, 2013).

3.2 Population and Sample

Target population of the research is 1299 teachers who work in İpek Yolu and Tuşba Districts of Van Province. Since it is not possible to reach the whole target population, sampling was carried out (Balci, 2010). It was decided by the researchers that a sample consisting of 300 people shall be sufficient for the research. While the specified sample was distributed to schools, cluster sampling method was taken into account by considering that the sizes of schools might have impact. In cluster sampling method, firstly, schools were ranked by their number of teachers. Schools where every ten teachers are employed are considered as a cluster. It was detected that schools with the least number of teachers have 10-19 teachers, and schools with the highest number of teachers have 40 and more teachers. In accordance with this, schools were classified as four clusters. Four schools from each cluster were taken. Teachers from each school were randomly selected according to the number of samples. The scales were distributed in accordance the sample, but 242 scales were taken into consideration since some of the scales were not returned, some were missing, some were filled incorrectly, and some gave extreme values.

3.3 Data Collection Tools

In the collection of the data of the research, "Favouritism Scale in School Management" which was developed by Erdem and Meriç (2011) and "Organizational Cynicism Scale"

which was developed by Brandes, Dharwadkar and Dean (1999) and adapted to Turkish by Karacaoğlu and İnce (2012) were used. "Favouritism Scale in School Management" scale was developed by researchers. Frequency, percentage, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation were used as descriptive statistics in the analysis of the data. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used with the aim of identifying whether there is a significant difference by t-test for gender, branch, professional seniority, and the number of teachers at schools. In order to determine the predictive power of favouritism in predicting cynicism, regression analysis was carried out. The scores in Likert type rating scale were evaluated as given in Table 1.

Table 1: Evaluation table of favouritism, cynicism, and correlation scales

Favouritism	Cynicism	Score Interval	Cynicism	Pearson Correlation	Levels
Never	Not agree at all	1.00-1.79	Not agree at all	Very weak	0.00-0.25
Rarely	Not agree	1.80-2.59	Not agree	Weak	0.26-0.49
Sometimes	Partly agree	2.60-3.39	Partly agree	Medium	0.50-0.69
Mostly	Frequently agree	3.40-4.19	Frequently agree	High	0.70-0.89
Always	Completely agree	4.20-5.00	Completely agree	Very high	0.90-1.00

4. Results and Discussion

Results of descriptive statistics related to the research, t-test, ANOVA, and regression analysis were given in the findings. Descriptive statistics on the average scores and standard deviations of the total scores of cynicism and favouritism and sub-dimensions of favouritism are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Average and Standard Deviation Values of Total Scores of Cynicism and Favouritism and Sub-Dimensions of Favouritism

Categories	Sub-Dimensions of Favouritism	n	$\bar{X}$	S
Cynicism Total		242	2.51	.86
Favouritism Total		242	2.13	.84
	Planning	242	2.16	.93
	Coordination	242	2.32	1.04
	Organizing	242	2.14	.96
	Evaluation	242	1.89	.89

As observed in Table 2, teachers stated that school administrators "rarely" ($\bar{X}$ =2.13) performed favouritism in all sub-dimensions of favouritism. When sub-dimensions of favouritism are checked, teachers stated that school administrators performed favouritism most in coordination sub-dimension ($\bar{X}$ =2.32) and least in evaluation sub-dimension ($\bar{X}$ =1.89). In other sub-dimensions, they stated that they performed favouritism rarely in planning ($\bar{X}$ =2.16) and organizing ($\bar{X}$ =2.14) sub-dimensions. Teachers' perception of cynicism was found as "not agree" ($\bar{X}$ =2.51).

While teachers think that administrators perform favouritism most respectively in “the planning of class distribution” ($\bar{X}$ =2.44), “giving leave” ($\bar{X}$ =2.40), and “not considering teachers’ complaints” ($\bar{X}$ =2.35), they think that administrators perform favouritism least respectively in “between teachers, according to their hometowns” ($\bar{X}$ =1.69), “related to the branches of teachers” ($\bar{X}$ =1.72), and “between teachers, according to their professional seniority” ($\bar{X}$ =1.84).

While the issues that teachers exhibit cynical behaviour most are respectively that “I talk to others about how things work in the institution I work” ($\bar{X}$ = 2.88), and that “I believe that what is said and what is done are different in the institution I work” ($\bar{X}$ =2.78), the issues that teachers exhibit cynical behaviour least are respectively that ($\bar{X}$ =2.14), “Whenever I think about the institution I work, I feel nervous” ($\bar{X}$ =2.17).

Average, standard deviation, and t-test analysis values of perceptions of favouritism of teachers who participated in the research and their level of cynicism by gender are given in Table 3.

Table 3: T-test analysis of favouritism and cynicism levels by gender variable

Categories	Sub-Dimensions	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	S	t	df	p
	Planning	Female	123	2.14	.88	-.30	240	.76
		Male	119	2.18	.98	-.30	235.49	
	Coordination	Female	123	2.40	1.10	1.10	240	.27
		Male	119	2.25	.97	1.10	237.92	
	Organizing	Female	123	2.09	.93	-.76	240	.44
		Male	119	2.19	1.00	-.76	237.20	
	Evaluation	Female	123	1.86	.83	-.56	240	.57
		Male	119	1.92	.94	-.56	234.22	
General Score of Favouritism		Female	123	2.12	.81	-.11	240	.91
		Male	119	2.13	.86	-.11	238.10	
General Score of Organizational Cynicism		Female	123	2.62	.91	2.08	240	.03*
		Male	119	2.39	.79	2.08	237.33	

*p<.05

As observed in Table 3, there is not a significant difference between groups in the planning, coordination, organizing, and evaluation sub-dimensions of favouritism and in general score of favouritism of teachers in terms of gender (p<.05). According to this, it can be stated that female and male teachers have similar perceptions about the favouritism in school management. Nevertheless, in total, perception of favouritism of male teachers ($\bar{X}$ =2.13) are higher compared to female teachers ($\bar{X}$ =2.12).

When the total score of organizational cynicism was checked, a significant difference was found between the opinions of female teachers and male teachers (t=2.08; p<.05). Female teachers ($\bar{X}$ =2.62) stated that they exhibit more cynical behaviours than male teachers ($\bar{X}$ =2.39).

ANOVA values aiming at determining the difference of teachers’ opinions about favouritism and cynicism by the number of teachers in schools are given in Table 4.

Table 4: ANOVA values of favouritism and cynicism by the number of teachers in schools

		Sum of Squares	df	Average of Squares	F	p
Planning	Between Groups	8.40	3	2.80	3.27	0.02*
	Within Groups	203.75	238	0.85		
	Total	212.15	241			
Coordination	Between Groups	6.78	3	2.26	2.11	0.09
	Within Groups	254.81	238	1.07		
	Total	261.6	241			
Organizing	Between Groups	10.59	3	3.53	3.91	0.00**
	Within Groups	214.73	238	0.90		
	Total	225.32	241			
Evaluation	Between Groups	7.01	3	2.33	3.01	0.03*
	Within Groups	184.72	238	0.77		
	Total	191.74	241			
Total Score of Favouritism	Between Groups	7.90	3	2.63	3.85	0.01*
	Within Groups	162.60	238	0.68		
	Total	170.50	241			
Organizational Cynicism	Between Groups	6.059	3	2.02	2.79	0.04*
	Within Groups	172.22	238	0.72		
	Total	178.28	241			

*p<.05, **p<.001

As observed in Table 4, apart from coordination, in total and sub-dimensions of favouritism, teachers' opinions about organizational cynicism differed by the number of teachers in the school ($p<.05$). When the source of difference was checked through Scheffe test, in all sub-dimensions and total scores, it was found out that there is a significant difference between the opinions of teachers who work in schools with 30-39 teachers and the opinions of teachers who work in schools with 40 or more teachers ($p<.05$). Average and standard deviation values by the number of teachers are given in Table 5.

As observed in Table 5. in planning, organizing, and evaluation sub-dimensions, and in the total of favouritism and cynicism, teachers who work in schools with 30-39 teachers ($\bar{X}=2.11-2.75$) stated that they performed more favouritism in planning, organizing, and evaluation sub-dimensions compared to teachers who work in schools with 40 and more teachers ($\bar{X}=1.68-1.96$). In cynicism dimension, teachers who work in schools with 30-39 teachers ($\bar{X}=2.11-2.75$) stated that they exhibit more cynical behaviours to teachers who work in schools with 10-19 students and teachers who work in schools with 40 and more teachers ($\bar{X}=1.68-1.96$).

Table 5: Average and Standard Deviation Values by the Number of Teachers

Categories	Number of Teachers	n	$\bar{X}$	S	
Sub-Dimensions of Favouritism	Planning	10-19 teachers	21	1.928	.767
		20-29 teachers	97	2.198	.960
		30-39 teachers*	55	2.445	.953
		40 and more teachers*	69	1.963	.894
		Total	242	2.164	.938
	Coordination	10-19 teachers	21	2.009	.844
		20-29 teachers	97	2.346	.989
		30-39 teachers	55	2.578	1.043
		40 and more teachers	69	2.197	1.136
		Total	242	2.327	1.041
	Organizing	10-19 teachers	21	1.825	.611
		20-29 teachers	97	2.149	.992
		30-39 teachers*	55	2.481	.901
		40 and more teachers*	69	1.966	1.005
		Total	242	2.144	.966
	Evaluation	10-19 teachers	21	1.696	.562
		20-29 teachers	97	1.967	.950
		30-39 teachers*	55	2.111	.924
		40 and more teachers*	69	1.683	.817
		Total	242	1.895	.891
Total Score of Favouritism	10-19 teachers	21	1.865	.658	
	20-29 teachers	97	2.165	.838	
	30-39 teachers*	55	2.404	.825	
	40 and more teachers*	69	1.952	.854	
	Total	242	2.133	.841	
Organizational Cynicism	10-19 teachers*	21	2.337	.715	
	20-29 teachers	97	2.538	.803	
	30-39 teachers*	55	2.755	.950	
	40 and more teachers*	69	2.337	.867	
	Total	242	2.513	.860	

Average, standard deviation, and t-test values of teachers' opinions about favouritism and cynicism by class and branch are given in Table 6.

As observed in Table 6, opinions of class and branch teachers do not show a significant difference in sub-dimensions of favouritism, total score of favouritism, and organizational cynicism ($p < .05$).

Table 6: Average, standard deviation, and t-test values
 of teachers' opinions about favouritism and cynicism by class and branch

Categories	Branch	n	$\bar{X}$	S	t	df	p	
Sub-Dimensions of Favouritism	Planning	Class	213	2.173	.936	.424	240	.672
		Branch	29	2.094	.964	.415	35.571	.681
	Coordination	Class	213	2.325	1.022	-.059	240	.953
		Branch	29	2.337	1.19	-.052	33.839	.959
	Organizing	Class	213	2.145	.9602	.040	240	.968
		Branch	29	2.137	1.032	.038	34.922	.970
	Evaluation	Class	213	1.896	.879	.050	240	.960
		Branch	29	1.887	.994	.045	34.230	.964
Total Score of Favouritism	Class	213	2.135	.828	.125	240	.901	
	Branch	29	2.114	.945	.113	34.103	.911	
Organizational Cynicism	Class	213	2.514	.862	.060	240	.952	
	Branch	29	2.504	.857	.061	36.143	.952	

Table 7: ANOVA Values Comparing Teachers' Opinions
 about Favouritism and Cynicism by Period of Service

Categories		Sum of Squares	df	Average of Squares	F	p	
Sub- Dimensions of Favouritism	Planning	Between Groups	1.48	3	.49	.55	.64
		Within Groups	210.67	238	.88		
		Total	212.15	241			
	Coordination	Between Groups	5.74	3	1.91	1.78	.15
		Within Groups	255.8	238	1.07		
		Total	261.60	241			
	Organizing	Between Groups	1.16	3	.38	.41	.74
		Within Groups	224.16	238	.94		
		Total	225.32	241			
Evaluation	Between Groups	.74	3	.24	.31	.81	
	Within Groups	190.99	238	.80			
	Total	191.74	241				
Total Score of Favouritism	Between Groups	.816	3	.27	.38	.76	
	Within Groups	169.69	238	.71			
	Total	170.50	241				
Organizational Cynicism	Between Groups	.741	3	.24	.33	.80	
	Within Groups	177.54	238	.74			
	Total	178.28	241				

ANOVA values comparing teachers' opinions about favouritism and cynicism by period of service are given in Table 7.

As observed in Table 7, teachers' opinions by their period of service show no significant difference between sub-dimensions of favouritism, total score of favouritism, and organizational cynicism ($p < .05$). Regression analysis about the predictive power of favouritism in predicting cynicism is given in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression analysis results of cynicism being predicted by favouritism

Model	R	R ²	Corrected R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
Favouritism	.47	.22	.21	.75	1.30

Dependent Variable: Cynicism

Predictors: (Fixed): Favouritism

As observed in Table 8, favouritism explains 22% of cynicism. It can be observed from Durbin-Watson values that there is not autocorrelation in the model (DW=1.30). ANOVA values of the predictive power of total score of favouritism in predicting cynicism are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Test of significance of the predictive power
of total score of favouritism in predicting cynicism

Model	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Sum of Squares	F	p
1 Regression	39.660	1	39.660	68.66	.00
Residual	138.621	240	.578		
Total	178,281	241			

Dependent Variable: Cynicism

Predictors: (Fixed): Favouritism

As observed in Table 9, when ANOVA values are checked, there is a significant relationship between favouritism and cynicism ($F=68.66$; $p < .001$). Analyses related to correlation, t-test, Beta and B values of the predictive power of total score of favouritism in predicting cynicism are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Regression analysis of the predictive
power of favouritism perceptions in predicting cynicism

Model	B	Standard Error	β	t	p	r
Fixed	1.49	.13		11.22	.000	.47
Favouritism	.49	.05	.47	8.28	.000	

When Table 10 is analysed, it can be observed that there is a medium-level significant and positive relationship between favouritism and cynicism ($r=0.47$). When B (regression equality) is analysed and other variables are kept fixed, favouritism explains 49% of cynicism. It is seen that favouritism is a significant predictor of organizational cynicism. Regression analysis of the predictive power of planning, coordination, organizing, and

evaluation, which are sub-dimensions of favouritism, in predicting cynicism is given in Table 11.

Table 11: Regression model of predictive power
 of sub-dimensions of favouritism in predicting cynicism

Model	R	R ²	Corrected R ²	Standard Error of the Prediction	Durbin-Watson
1	.50	.25	.24	.74	1.38

a. Dependent Variable: Cynicism

b. Predictors: (Fixed), Evaluation, Planning, Coordination, Organizing

As observed in Table 11, sub-dimensions of favouritism explain 25% of cynicism ($R^2=0,25$). When Durbin-Watson test is checked (1,38), it can be observed that there is not autocorrelation in the model. It was detected in the research that 25% of total variance of cynicism perception of teachers [$R=.50$, $R^2=.25$] can be explained through behaviours of favouritism of administrators, and 75% change in the score of organizational cynicism can be explained through other variables. Significance test on the level of prediction of cynicism by sub-dimensions of favouritism is given in Table 12.

Table 12: Significance test on the level
 of prediction of cynicism by sub-dimensions of favouritism

Model	Sum of Squares	Sd	Average of Squares	F	p
1 Regression	45.61	4	11.40	20.36	.00*
Residual	132.67	237	.56		
Total	178.28	241			

a. Dependent Variable: Cynicism

b. Predictors: (Fixed), Evaluation, Planning, Coordination, Organizing

* $p<.001$

When Table 12 is analysed, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between sub-dimensions of favouritism and cynicism ($F=20.36$; $p>.01$). Analyses related to correlation, t-test, Beta and B values of the predictive power of sub-dimensions of favouritism in predicting cynicism are given in Table 13.

Table 13: Regression analysis of the predictive power of
 sub-dimensions of favouritism in predicting cynicism

Variables	B	Standard Error B	β	t	p	r
Fixed	1.49	.13		11.32	.00	
Planning	-.02	.08	-.02	-.31	.75	.33
Coordination	.32	.07	.38	4.20	.00*	.49
Organizing	.00	.09	.00	.05	.95	.39
Evaluation	.16	.08	.173	2.06	.04*	.42

* $p<.05$

When Table 13 is analysed, it is observed that there is a significant positive and medium level relationship between sub-dimensions of favouritism and cynicism. While the highest level of relationship is between coordination and cynicism ($r=0.49$), it is followed by evaluation ($r=0.42$), organizing ($r=0.39$), and planning ($r=0.33$). When t-test values are checked, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between coordination and cynicism ($t=4.20$; $p<.001$) and between evaluation and cynicism ($t=2.06$; $p<.05$). When Beta (Standardized regression coefficient) values are checked, relative order of importance on cynicism is as follows: coordination, evaluation, planning, and organizing. When regression model is analysed and other predictive variables are kept fixed, one unit increase in the coordination sub-dimension of favouritism causes 32% increase in cynicism and one unit increase in the evaluation sub-dimension of favouritism causes 16% increase in cynicism. The most significant dimensions which affect teachers' perception of cynicism are coordination and evaluation sub-dimensions of favouritism.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

As a result of the research, it is observed that there is a significant positive and medium level relationship between favouritism and organizational cynicism. It is seen that the perception of favouritism in schools is a significant predictor of the level of organizational cynicism. In other words, as the behaviours of favouritism of school administrators increase, cynical behaviours of teachers also increase. The studies carried out by Gül (2016), Kalağan and Güzeller (2010), Karademir (2016) and Turhan and Gül (2019) also support these results. Behaviours of favouritism of school administrators cause hatred, anger, and unhappiness in teachers (Keskinçilic & Oğuz, 2016). It was also determined that teachers' organizational cynicism perception increased as school administrators' favouritism behaviours increased.

In schools, the perception of favoritism is a significant predictor of the level of organizational cynism. School administrators should not exhibit favoritism behaviors in order to prevent the teachers organizational cynism attitudes and behaviors in educational organizations (Turhan & Erol, 2019). As a consequence of the research, the argument that teachers' perception of behaviours of favouritism of school administrators is low but they sometimes exhibit favouritism behaviours even if it is rare shows parallelism with the results of researches carried out by Akan and Zengin (2018), Gül (2016), Kazancı (2010), Meriç and Erdem (2013), Okçu and Uçar (2016), Polat and Kazak (2014) and Karademir (2016). It can be assessed as positive that favouritism is perceived in a low level in schools. However, acts of favouritism are observed in school although it is rare. On the other hand, in the study carried out by Turhan and Erol (2019), teachers stated that school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism in a medium level. On the other hand, school principals' favouritism behaviours undermine the sense of justice among teachers at school and cause getting away from work, absence, low loyalty to work and organization, having a distance towards work and work stress (Dağlı & Akyol, 2019).

In the research, teachers stated that school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism least by hometown, branch, and professional seniority; and most by coordination sub-dimension. In addition, teachers have the opinion that school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism especially in issues of planning class distribution, identifying syllabus, giving leave, and considering demands/complaints. In the research carried out by Gül (2016), the fact that the perception of favouritism in the processes of planning and organizing was found high shows parallelism with the result of this research. Again, in the research carried out by Aydoğan (2009), the finding that teachers thought school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism most in planning class distribution shows consistency with the result of this research.

In this research, teachers stated that school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism in the process of evaluation in a low level. It was observed that there is not a significant difference between perceptions of behaviours of favouritism of female teachers and male teachers. In the study carried out by Turhan and Erol (2019), it was detected that there is not a significant difference between perceptions of favouritism of teachers by gender variable. Additionally, in this research, female teachers' perception of cynicism is significantly higher than male teachers' perception. However, in contrary to the findings here, in the study carried out by Karademir (2016), it was found out that male teachers perceive more favouritism of school administrators compared to female teachers.

In this research, teachers who work in schools with 30-44 teachers stated more cynical behaviours and more behaviours of favouritism of school administrators compared to teachers who work in schools with 45 and more teachers. It is observed that the number of teachers in school affects favouritism. It might result from the fact that as the number of teachers increases, institutionalization also increases. Institutionalization brings loyalty to the organization not to individuals and it enables the continuity of the organization. Again, in this study, teachers' perceptions of favouritism and cynicism do not vary by period of service and branches. Also, teachers stated that school administrators carry out favouritism least for "hometowns of teachers".

In the study conducted by Aydoğan (2009), teachers stated that school administrators partially display positive attitudes and behaviors and also partially have cynical beliefs, emotions, attitudes and behaviors towards schools. According to the research, it can be stated that teachers' perception of organizational cynicism is low. It can be evaluated as something positive. Although teachers' perceptions of school administrators' favoritism behaviors are low, favoritism and organizational cynism are seen in schools in Turkish Education System. In the study carried out by Turhan and Erol (2019), it was observed that teachers' perception of cynicism is on a medium level. In this research, it is observed that female teachers exhibit more cynical behaviours than male teachers. It can be concluded that since female teachers are more emotional compared to male teachers, it might be the reason behind it (Kahveci & Demirtaş, 2013; Turhan & Erol, 2019). Female teachers prefer more staying silent in expressing their opinions, criticising, and presenting suggestions compared to male teachers. In addition to this, it is observed

that female teachers have more negative beliefs, emotions, and behaviours towards institutions they work compared to male teachers (Kahveci & Demirtaş, 2013; Turhan & Erol, 2019).

The fact that school administrators exhibit behaviours of favouritism in educational organizations causes teachers to exhibit cynical behaviours (Turhan & Gül, 2019). Teachers' perception of organizational cynicism varies by leadership approach of school administrators. Perception of organizational cynicism of teachers who work in schools where democratic management approach is performed is lower compared to the teachers who work in schools where indifferent management is performed (Balay, Kaya & Çülha, 2013). In organizations where there is no skill management, behaviours of favouritism increase, and organizational commitment levels decrease. Also, it shall decrease the perception of favouritism if school administrators become objective, equal, and fair in their behaviours towards teachers (Aytaç, 2015; Aydın, 2016; Erdem & Meriç, 2013). The high perception of cynicism of teachers in schools decreases their sense of belonging, motivation, and productivity. Lower perception of favouritism shall also decrease cynicism since it is the reason of high cynicism.

6. Recommendations

Within the scope of this research, following suggestion were developed:

- School administrators should stay away from practices which may cause perception of favouritism among teachers.
- School administrators should take a proactive role in preventing problems caused by favouritism and cynicism. If school administrators enable teachers to take part in decision-making processes and practices, it shall decrease their perception of cynicism. Teachers should be encouraged to talk about the problems they encounter in schools. In this context, teachers and other staff at school should be given the opportunity to express their opinions freely. School administrators should participate in social and cultural activities with teachers, they should know them and develop the understanding of 'our school'.
- In the research, it is observed that female teachers exhibit more cynical behaviours compared to male teachers. In the context of providing gender equality, female teachers should be supported more to be more active in their roles in management processes and teaching-learning activities by the school administrators.
- Awareness and knowledge of school administrators and teachers about the causes and consequences of favouritism and cynicism can help them eliminate the causes of such unwanted behaviours. Trainings and briefings aiming at creating awareness about the identification, proving, and results of these behaviours should be provided both for teachers and school administrators.
- Qualitative researches can be carried out through meta-analysis studies which discuss the relationship between favouritism and cynicism.

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